

THE EFFECTS OF ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT IN TEAM WORKING ON CREATIVITY AND PERSONAL INITIATIVE OF EMPLOYEES

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Received: 23.02.2018

Accepted: 17.06.2018

ABSTRACT

Organizational support is one of the important dimensions of team working concept. The culture that will encourage employees to take the initiative and be creative requires top management support. The research question of this study is how organizational support exerts influence on take the initiative by team members and creativity of the employees. Therefore, this study aims to shed light on the relationship among organizational support, creativity and personal initiative. As a result of test of the hypotheses, positive and significant relationships between Organizational Support and Creativity and between Organizational Support and Personal Initiative have been supported. Managerial implications of these results are that if the employees feel the support of the management, they will be willing to take the initiative and they will unleash their creative potentials.

Keywords: Team working, organizational support, creativity, personal initiative.

INTRODUCTION

In today's cluttered and highly competitive organizational environment, organizations should set up teams and also empower the employees working in teams. It should also encourage the employees to take the initiative and to use their creativeness. These are related to the climate prevailing within the organization. The organizational climate is a result of the organizational culture. The culture that will encourage employees to take the initiative and be creative requires first support learning and change (Koçel, 2011). The general characteristics of the learning culture in an organization can be summarized as follows; being open to experience, encouragement of risk taking responsibility, being open to learning from mistakes (Mcgill & Slocum, 1993). Making mistakes and taking lessons from the mistakes are the part of learning process. It is necessary to take responsibility and risk in making mistakes. In order to encourage employees to take responsibility and risk, there must be tolerance. This can be achieved through the support of the top management. In order to encourage employees to take the initiative in organizations, managers need to create such an environment within the organization. To create such an environment, the following items are necessary activities; encouraging activities, where possible, non-formal meetings may be held, display fault tolerance, mistakes should be seen as a teaching experience, awarding personnel who has innovative ideas, keeping non-formal communication channels open, creation of teams for future projects, avoiding paperwork (İbicioğlu & Doğan, 2006) (Daft, 2004).

The encouragement of employees with innovative ideas in organizations can be related to the concept of intrapreneurship. In the study conducted by Kuratko, Montagno and Hornsby in 1990, four factors were found to be important in the development of intrapreneurship within the organization. These are management support, organizational structure, rewarding and the possibility to use the resources which are available to the members. In the study conducted by Joseph in 2004, seven factors have been emphasized in terms of the development of intrapreneurship. These can be summarized as follows: be aware of risk and take affordable risk in case of an opportunity, authorization and empowerment, acceptance of change and uncertainty, network organization structure, encouragement of entrepreneurship and motivation applications, promotion of team work, fault tolerance (Srivastavaand & Agrawal, 2010).

The aim of this study is to explore the relationship among organizational support, creativity and personal initiative. Organizational support is one of the important dimensions of team working concept. Therefore, research question of this study is how organizational support exerts influence on take the initiative by team members and creativity of the employees.

CONCEPTUAL BACKGROUND

Organizational Support in Team Working

Team working is an important factor for firms today. Increasing pressure on employees, having to perform their tasks with fewer employees, faster, and higher quality and more customer responsiveness are all leading to the need for teamwork at firms (Levi & Slem, 1995). Creating successful work teams requires to provide the related conditions that supports team working (Katzenbach & Smith, 1993). The team is a small organism within the organization, consisting of people with complementary skills, dedicated to their performance goals and their mutual goals for which they are responsible. The members of this team share a common goal and are coordinated by a leader. A team may be part of an organization's operation, or it may be a mechanism used to evaluate and change an organization, such as Quality Circles and Total Quality Management (Levi & Slem, 1995).

When study on team working, it is first necessary to define the nature of team success. In the research on teamwork, they used various scales to examine the workings of the groups and to analyze their effectiveness. Most of these scales focus on the inner workings of teams and try to show the relationship between these scales and various success criteria. According to Hackman (1987) there are three basic team success definitions. These; tasks, social relations and individuals. From a management standpoint, the definition of team success is a performance in a task. Successful teams do their job better than others (Hackman, 1987). There are several factors in the literature that affect the success of teamwork. Hackman (1986) suggested that there are 5 factors for teams to work successfully. Hackman's model expresses five support factors necessary for the development and successful use of teams (Hackman, 1986). Teams need to clearly identify their goals and direction so they can focus on their efforts and assess their performance. There is a need for a good lead to set these goals and direct the team to the right goals (Katzenbach & Smith, 1993). This leadership, which will be fed by organizational support, is one of the important factors that will enable successful team work. Workgroups involved in organizational support provided by organizational support are more focused on success than those in organizational organizations (Levi & Slem, 1995).

Creativity

Creativity means developing new ideas and new ways of doing new things. Creativity also carries new risks at the same time. Because new ideas may or may not produce the intended positive results. Moreover, creativity requires departing from the status quo, traditional approaches and habits embedded in organizational systems and practices (Zhou & George, 2001). Thus, participation in creative activities can be risky and, if unsuccessful, employees who start these activities may experience negative consequences. For this reason, employees may prefer to use their creativity only when they perceive that creative performance has the potential to be

effective, and new and useful ideas that others in the organization can support can be generated (LePine & Van Dyne, 1998).

Having an organizational climate that supports the employee's creative performance positively affects the employee's creativity performance. This judgment is consistent with organizational creativity literature (Amabile, 1988) (Oldham & Cummings, 1996) (Scott & Bruce, 1994) (Shalley, 1991) (Shalley, 1995) (Woodman, Sawyer, & Griffin, 1993). Recent research on organizational creativity has shown that organizational conditions and intra-organizational practices can play an important role in promoting employee creativity. For example, organizational conditions can support creative performance by directing employees' attention and cognitive energy towards the generation of new and useful ideas. Moreover, previous theories and research on organizational creativity suggest that organizational conditions require employees to direct attention to creativity and maintain their image and energy in order to encourage creativity to be used as an organizational activity (Zhou & George, 2001) .

Personal Initiative

Recent studies have suggested that individual performance may have an impact on organizational effectiveness. These dimensions are explained as "intrapreneurship", "organizational citizenship behavior", "organizational spontaneity", "general work behavior" and "contextual performance" (Frese, Kring, Soose, & Zempel, 1996) (Frese & Zapf, 1994) (Hacker, 1985) (Carver & Scheier, 1982). However, it is argued that future workplaces will require more personal initiative to people than their old counterparts and that existing concepts of performance and organizational behavior are desirably more reactive (Frese & Zapf, 1994) (Frese, Kring, Soose, & Zempel, 1996) (Frese & Fay, 2001). From this point of view, the personal initiative is a self-initiating and proactively defined work behavior from the superintendent of the obstacles to achieve a goal (Frese, Kring, Soose, & Zempel, 1996). In other words, it allows people to deal with work stress more actively, such as personal initiative, stress, unemployment, career changes or entrepreneurship (Raabe , Frese , & Beehr, 2007).

According to another definition, personal initiative is a behavior syndrome resulting in an individual adopting an active, self-directed approach that goes beyond recruitment and officially necessary in a particular job (Carver & Scheier, 1982). In addition, personal initiative are also sharpened and partially changed the organizational citizenship behavior, innovation, entrepreneurship, business performance, internal motivation and self-regulation (Frese, Kring, Soose, & Zempel, 1996).

RESEARCH MODEL AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

The Conceptual Research Model presented in Figure 1 aims to explore the relationship among Organizational Support, Creativity, Personal Initiative.

Figure 1. Conceptual Research Model

The Relationship between Organizational Support and Personal Initiative

In the literature, there are studies investigating the relationship between organizational support and personal initiative (Carver & Scheier, 1982)(Frese & Day, 2001) (Frese & Zapf, 1994). Carver and Scheier (1982) stated that in their research, employees feel more personal initiative behind organizational support. Frese and Day (2001) also argue that organizational support influences personal initiation behavior in employees. According to another study; it is supported that the behavior of taking personal initiative in the organizational climates where organizational support is more common is displayed more easily (Frese & Zapf, 1994). Thus, in the light of the existing literature we hypothesize that:

H₁: Organizational Support has a positive effect on Personal Initiative.

The Relationship between Organizational Support and Creativity

Firms may prefer to emphasize their support for creativity through perceived organizational support for creativity, to the extent that an employee encourages, respects, rewards and recognizes creative creativity. Employees can try to be creative when they perceive that their creativity is evaluated and supported by the company (Scott & Bruce, 1994). Because under these conditions the potential risk associated with creativity is reduced the most. However, the perception of creativity in the firm must be high.

As mentioned earlier, exhibiting creativity behavior can be costly for an organization member. It is never easy to try to put new approaches into an existing system. Because it may or may not be successful to promote ways of doing something new and useful. Employees will try to do so only when they think that creativity is potentially effective. If employees perceive that management systems and practices in an organization support creative activities, it is likely that managers will be welcomed and accepted the remediation proposals, and employees will feel that their inputs are meaningful and effective (Zhou & George, 2001).

Thus, in the light of the existing literature we hypothesize that:

H₂: Organizational Support has a positive effect on Creativity.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Five-point Likert scale was used in the survey. This research is a quantitative and cross-sectional research. Firstly the reliability and validity of the scales were determined. Subsequently, the hypotheses of the theoretical model were tested by structural equation modeling method. This method is good for eliminating measurement errors (Civelek, 2018). AMOS and SPSS statistics programs were used for analyses.

Measures and Sampling

The scales adopted from prior studies were used to measure the dimensions. The scale is ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. 5-point Likert scale was used. More than 98 distributed, 94 valid questionnaires were gathered from a prominent logistics company in Turkey. For measuring the Personal Initiative, the scale adopted by Frese et al was used (Frese, Kring, Soose, & Zempel, 1996). For measuring the Organizational Support in Team Working the scale developed by Levi and Slem was used (Levi & Slem, 1995). For measuring the Creativity the scale developed by Zhou and George was used (Zhou & George, 2001).

Construct Validity and Reliability

After the data purification, process 8 items were included in the confirmatory factor analysis. Confirmatory factor analysis was performed in order to determine convergent validity, (Anderson & Gerbing, 1988). CFA results indicated that the model has adequate fit indice values: $\chi^2/DF = 1.386$, CFI=0.981, IFI=0.982, RMSEA= 0.064. CMIN is The Likelihood Ratio Chi-Square Test. Analysis shows the conformity of the initial model and acquired model. A CMIN/DF ratio is under the threshold level of 3 (Bagozzi & Yi, 1990). Furthermore, other fit indices exceeded their recommended thresholds.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis Results are shown in Table 1 and standardized factor loads of each item are larger than 0.5 and significant. Accordind to the results, the convergent validity of the scales are determined. Average variance extracted values were also calculated. Results are close to or beyond the threshold level (i.e. 0.5)

(Byrne, 2010). Reliability of each construct individually calculated. Composite reliability and Cronbach α values are close to or beyond the threshold level (i.e. 0.7) (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

Table 1. Confirmatory Factor Analysis Results

Variables	Items	Standardized Factor Loads	Unstandardized Factor Loads
Personal Initiative	INSA0335	0.795	1
	INSA0133	0.845	1.337
	INSA0234	0.930	1.465
Creativity	CRTV0131	0.633	1
	CRTV0232	0.885	2.194
Organizational Support	TWOS0213	0.647	1
	TWOS0112	1.005	1.618
	TWOS0415	0.506	0.908

p<0.05 for all items

Descriptive statistics of the constructs, composite reliabilities, average variance extracted values, Cronbach α values and Pearson correlation coefficients are shown in Table 2. Additionally, in Table 2. The diagonals demonstrate the square root of AVE values of each variable. As swonn in the Table 2., the square root of AVE values are beyond the correlation coefficient in the same column. This result confirm the discriminant validity of the scales used.

Table 2. Construct Descriptives, Correlation and Reliability

Variables	1	2	3
1.Personal Initiative	(.858)		
2.Creativity	.516*	(.769)	
3.Organizational Support	.304*	.259*	(.749)
Composite reliability	.893	.738	.780
Average variance ext.	.737	.592	.562
Cronbach α	.885	.701	.749

*p < 0.05

Note: Diagonals show the square root of AVEs.

Test of Hypotheses

Structural model has been analyzed by using AMOS 23. To test the hypotheses, maximum likelihood estimation methods and the covariance matrix of the items were used. The absolute and relative goodness-of-fit indices of the model were evaluated. In this analysis, the following indices were used: The absolute goodness of fit indices are the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) and the χ^2 goodness of fit statistic. The relative goodness of fit indices are the comparative fit index (CFI) and the incremental fit index (IFI).

Table 3. Hypotheses Test Results

Relationships	Standardized Coefficients	Unstandardized Coefficients
Organizational Support → Creativity	0.358*	0.336*
Organizational Support → Personal Initiative	0.308*	0.342*

*p < 0.05

As shown in Figure 2, structural model fit indices adequately indicate model fit. χ^2/DF value is 2.637 and within threshold levels (i.e. between 2 and 5). CFI and IFI are 0.909 and 0.912 respectively. RMSEA is 0.083. As shown in Table 3, when H_1 are H_2 are accepted. These results of the hypotheses indicate a positive and significant relationship between Organizational Support and Creativity, between Organizational Support and Personal Initiative.

Figure 2. Results of SEM Analysis

DISCUSSION

Findings and Managerial Implications

This study aimed to explore the relationship among organizational support, creativity and personal initiative. Organizational support is one of the important dimensions of team working concept. At the beginning of this study it was assumed that organizational support has positive effect on take the initiative by team members and increases the creativity of them. Therefore, hypotheses were put forward in the same direction. As a result of test of the hypotheses, positive and significant relationships between Organizational Support and Creativity and between Organizational Support and Personal Initiative have been supported.

In case of the employees feel the support of the management, they are willing to take the initiative because of don't hesitate to make mistake. When creative employees feel the support in the organization climate, they can unleash their creative potentials.

Limitations and Suggestions for Future Research

It is worth to mention some limitations of this study which may have also lead the way for further research on this topic. First, this study explores the relationship among organizational support, creativity and personal initiative of the employees that only works in logistics sector. Besides, this study conducted on the sample consists of the employess working in only one company. Therefore, this should be considered as another limitation of this study. Further studies may be conducted on different employees working in different sectors and different sample size.

TAKIM ÇALIŞMASINDA ÖRGÜTSEL DESTEĞİN ÇALIŞANLARDA YARATICILIK VE KİŞİSEL İNİSYATİF ÜZERİNE ETKİSİ

ÖZ

Örgütsel destek takım çalışması kavramının önemli boyutlarından biridir. Çalışanları inisiyatif alma ve yaratıcı olma konusunda teşvik edecek örgüt kültürü üst yönetimin desteği ile ortaya çıkabilmektedir. Bu çalışmanın araştırma sorusu, takım üyelerinin inisiyatif alması ve yaratıcılıkları üzerine örgütsel desteğin nasıl etkili olduğudur. Bu nedenle, bu çalışma örgütsel destek, yaratıcılık ve inisiyatif arasındaki ilişkiye ışık tutmayı amaçlamaktadır. Hipotez testleri sonucunda, örgütsel destek ve yaratıcılık arasında ve örgütsel destek ve kişisel inisiyatif arasında anlamlı ve pozitif yönde bir ilişki bulunmuştur. Sonuç olarak; çalışanlar yönetimin desteğini arkalarında hissederlerse inisiyatif alma konusunda daha istekli olurlar ve yaratıcı potansiyelleri ortaya çıkar.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Takım çalışması, örgütsel destek, yaratıcılık, kişisel inisiyatif

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